

**LISTENING SKILL AS AN INDISPENSABLE TOOL TO EFFECTIVE
TEACHING OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN NIGERIA.**

By

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Abstract

The research surveyed the importance of effective listening for successful teaching of English as a second language in Nigeria. The researchers carried out the research by visiting some schools to find out how far the teachers and learners are making use of listening skills for effective teaching. They also observed and recorded some of the factors that hinder effective listening in the process of teaching and learning of English. They discovered that unconducive environment, use of poor teaching skills, lack of motivation of teachers etc. constitute obstacles to effective use of listening skills in teaching and learning of English. The researchers proffered solutions to the problems that are facing effective listening skills.

Keywords: Listening, indispensable, tool, effective, teaching, English.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the study.

Listening skill is one of the four skills in language learning. It is the first linguistic skill and in fact a very important skill as far as teaching language is concerned. No effective teaching and learning of any subject is possible without listening skill. Commenting on the concept of listening, Nwabunze, D.C (2015) states that listening carries a large chunk of the communication load in any setting, both formal and informal. It is about the most important area in communication. This is because today, people, institutions and organisations rely more and more on oral means of exchanging information be it in social-circles, work places, homes and schools. He further explains that everybody needs to listen: students who largely depend on how well they can retain information for the purpose of passing their examination, and for the manager who needs to know the happenings in every sector of his organization in order for him to make the right decisions and ensure maximum input for staff; listening is vital. Parents need to listen to their children to know their needs and problems, and how to tackle them. Health workers need to listen to their patients in order to know how to handle their health problems. In the law court, the lawyers and judges need to listen to listen attentively to their client in order for justice to prevail. Stanton (2004) states that listening is not automatic. It is crucial and central to successful communication. Unless everybody listens and understands a message, there cannot be any communication. He maintains that listening is not a passive activity. It is active. This is because a man who listens

because he has something to say does so to a degree to one who has something to say. The latter can hardly be a source of inspiration to others. So the only thing that counts is that of the speaker who alternatively absorbs and expresses ideas.

It is necessary to note that listening and hearing are two different concepts. Hearing comes before listening but listening entails attending to some speech sounds, putting interest to the sounds with the aim of comprehending what it is all about and if necessary making use of it; hearing does not go to this extent.

This paper is aimed at finding out the concept of listening skills, some qualities of good listening habit, what can inhibit good listening skills and how to improve listening skills especially in the teaching of English as a second language in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Listening is an indispensable tool to the harmonious existence of man in this universe. It is important in the teaching of all courses in the schools in general and in the teaching of English language in particular. But, it is lamentable to note that many people do not lay emphasis to effective listening skills. Some teachers are not left out in this neglect, especially teachers in some institutions of learning. Consequently this poses some challenges to effective teaching and learning of many courses especially English language in our schools.

The Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to find out the role of listening skills to the effective teaching and learning of English language as a second language in

Nigeria. The study also aims at finding the causes of poor listening skills in a typical English classroom and to proffer solutions to the problem.

The Significance of the Study

This study is important in the sense that it will enable the classroom teachers to appreciate the importance of listening to effective teaching and learning. It will also help the teachers especially the teachers of English to put more effort to make their students have conducive teaching environment so they will be able to listen effectively. It will also help the educational policy makers and planners to provide fund that will help in providing conducive teaching and learning environment in order to help the learners to learn effectively.

The Area and Scope of the Study

The study concentrated on the teaching and learning of English in SS1 in Orumba South Local Government Area of Anambra State.

The Methodology of the Research

The researchers took a field investigation of the work by visiting some secondary schools in Orumba South Local Government Area. They observed the teaching and learning of English in those schools. This was aimed at finding out whether the students had effective listening skills as the lessons went on. They also investigated the teaching environment to know whether it was conducive for effective teaching and what could be done to improve this situation.

The Review of Related Literature

The literature for this study was reviewed under three subheadings namely:

- a) The conceptual framework
- b) The theoretical framework
- c) The empirical framework

The conceptual framework

The following concepts were reviewed:

- a) Listening
- b) Indispensable
- c) Tool
- d) Effective
- e) Teaching
- f) English
- g) Nigeria

The Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary 6th Edition defines the following concepts as follows:

Listening: to pay attention to something that you can hear, to take notice of what somebody says to you so that you can follow their advice or believe them.

Indispensable: essential, too important to be without. E.g. A good dictionary is indispensable for learning a foreign language.

Tool: An instrument such as a hammer that you hold in your hand and use for making things, repairing things, a thing that helps you do your job or to achieve, a person who is used or controlled by another person or group.

Effective: producing the result that is wanted or intended, producing a successful result, coming into use.

Teacher:the work of a teacher, the particular person or group, especially about politics, religion or society that are taught to other people.

English:the language of Britain, Ireland, North America, Australia and some other countries. English language and Literature as a subject of study.

Nigeria: Nigeria is one of the largest countries in Africa. It is popularly described by her patriotic citizens as the giant of Africa. It is the most populous country in Africa with very large land mass.

Theoretical framework

There are certain linguistic theories that are needed for this study. These include:

- a) Second language acquisition theory.
- b) Behaviourism: learning as habit formation.

The first coherent theory of learning was the behaviourist theory based mainly on the study conducted by Pavlov in the Soviet Union and of Skinner in the United States. The simple but powerful theory states that learning is a mechanical process of habit formation and proceeds by means of the frequent reinforcement of a stimulus-response sequence. This all important theory had a very enormous impact on learning psychology and on language teaching. It provided the theoretical underpinning of the widely used audio-lingual method of the 1950s and the 1960s. This method which will be familiar to many language teachers laid down a set of guiding methodological principles based firstly on the behaviourist stimulus-

response concept and secondly on an assumption that second language learning should reflect and imitate the perceived process of mother tongue learning. Some of these precepts were:

- a) Never translate.
- b) New language should always be dealt with in the sequence: hear, speak, read and write.
- c) Frequent repetition is essential to effective learning.
- d) All errors must be immediately corrected.

The basic exercise technique of a behaviourist methodology is pattern practice, particularly in the form of language laboratory drills. The implication of this theory is that listening is very important in second language learning. The learners should pay very critical attention to native speakers in order to achieve native speakers' competence or at least near native speakers' competence.

Empirical Studies

Some linguists have made some indebt studies of the concept of listening as a very important linguistic skill. For instance, Kwekowe (2003) defines listening as “complex psychological process involving hearing, selecting, interpretation and understanding of the significance of the sensory experiences”. He explained that listening is hearing with attention that involves perception, motivation, thinking ability and empathy. Some people might think that hearing is the same as listening, but this is not so. Hearing is a psychological sensory process by which auditory impressions are received by the ears and transmitted to the

brain. Listening is a deliberate action. Through listening, information and knowledge is acquired. It is a receptive skill through which learning takes place.

There is a natural tendency that we listen to noise. If the noise is a meaningful one, there is every tendency that we try to interpret the meaning and if necessary make use of it. Nelson (1989) as cited in Kwekowe states that listening is a dual affair. He recorded that listening and hearing are clearly perceived as two distinguishable phases. The hearing of a sound and the interpretation of a sound of a process, usually called aural assimilation are different concepts. If the first phase of hearing is identified as the perception of the sound, only then it is the second phase of the aural symbols perceived which has come to be largely accepted as the definition of listening.

Rosonberger as cited in Kwekowe (2006) identifies four major steps in listening process: that of hearing, of understanding, evaluating and of response. This implies that immediately we hear a sound, there is a natural tendency that we try to have an understanding of the sound. The next thing is that we consider and examine the sound. This can be shown through some sensory movements like demonstration of a facial response or an audible response as the need arises. Listening is very important in the effective teaching and learning of English. In fact, no meaningful teaching and learning can take place without the learner listening effectively to the teacher with an aim of getting the necessary information and knowledge which he desires.

Types of listening

There are three major types of listening namely:

- a) Listening to learn: this is a type of listening which the learner needs to employ in his learning process. It is mostly needed and used in the classroom. Students listen attentively to lectures in order to acquire the relevant knowledge that will help them do well in their examination. Listening is particularly needed in the teaching of spoken English where the students listen to the native speakers in order to learn the correct articulation of words.
- b) Listening to enjoy: this is the type of listening which one employs when one hears some musical sounds. He listens to the rhythm of the music and enjoys the patterns of the instruments and songs
- c) Listening to evaluate: here, the listener tries to get the gist of the whole story or sound in order to pass some judgements. This judgement can be positive or negative depending on the listener. If the listener is not biased, there is every tendency that he will pass an objective judgement. He listens to gather information which will finally help him to form an opinion or have an experience.

Kwekowe (2006) as contained in Okoli, V.C and Eukoha, Celina (2014) noted these studies as direction for effective listening.

- a) Listen to the instructions the first time they are given.
- b) Listen carefully to each detail.
- c) Picture each detail in your mind.
- d) Put down the main ideas.
- e) Ask questions about doubtful points.
- f) Repeat the direction, explanations or instructions aloud when possible
- g) Repeat the directions or think them through as you carry them out.

Methodology for data collection

The researchers visited some secondary schools in Orumba South Local Government Area of Anambra State to find out how the students listen to their English language teachers. The population for the study were SS1 students in some selected secondary schools. These schools were:

- a) Girls Secondary School, Umunze
- b) Community secondary school, Ihite
- c) Victory Girls secondary school, Ezira
- d) Boys secondary school, Isulo

The researchers visited these schools and observed the teaching and learning of English language. They visited the schools four consecutive times and made the following observations and discoveries:

- a) That most of the students were not effectively listening to the teachers.
- b) That the classroom environment was not conducive for effective teaching. For instance, the population of the students were much for the teachers to control.
- c) That there were no adequate teaching materials for the lessons
- d) That the teachers were not happy and as such did not show much interest and dedication to teaching.

Summary of findings

The researchers after watching the teaching, interrogated both the teachers and the principals. They made the following discoveries:

- a) That the school did not have enough teachers of English language
- b) That the large classroom did not give room for effective teaching on the part of the teachers and effective learning on the part of the students. While some students in front of the classroom were listening to their teachers, those at the back were playing away their time.
- c) That the schools did not have enough classroom to enable them share the students into manageable size
- d) That there were no teaching materials; consequently, this made the teaching abstract and the students therefore lost interest in teaching.
- e) That teacher's remuneration and motivation was very poor. This made them lose interest in teaching. They were not happy because "a hungry man is an angry man"

Way forward

The way forward to these problems should be that the educational planners, policy makers, educational implementers, parents, patriotic individuals and voluntary organization should put all their hands on deck and provide adequate fund for education. The fund will go a long way to be used to provide the following:

- a) Enough qualified teachers.
- b) Enough instructional materials for teaching.
- c) Conducive environment for teaching and learning.
- d) Adequate motivation of teachers.

When all these are provided, there will be effective teaching. Effective teaching will no doubt bring about effective learning because the learners will listen attentively.

Conclusion

Listening is an indispensable skill to the teaching and learning of all courses in general and to the teaching of English in particular. Man cannot exist peacefully in an environment without having an effective listening skill. For effective listening to take place, there should be a conducive environment especially as it concerns listening in the educational setting. Nicholas et al. quoted in Okoli, V.C and Erukoha, Celine (2014); a listener should do the following in order to improve his thought speed:

- a) He should try to anticipate what a speaker is going to talk about on the basis of what he had already said; ask yourself, what is he trying to get at? What point is he going to make?
- b) Mentally summarize what the speaker has been saying
- c) Weigh the speaker's evidence by mentally questioning it as he presents facts. Continually ask yourself, are they accurate? Do they come from an unprejudiced source? Am I getting the full picture or is he telling me only what will prove his point?
- d) Listen between the lines. A speaker doesn't always put what is important into words. The changing tones and volumes of his voice may have a meaning, so may his facial expressions, the gesture he makes with his hands and the movement of his body. A good listener is not easily provoked by the

speaker's choice of words, no matter how offensive they may sound. The implication is that the students should try to develop effective skills in the classroom especially in the teaching and learning of English whether the teacher offends them or not.

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